

Praying for Others: How Does It Affect Us?

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Every call and message that I receive these days end with a request, “please pray for me/us.” The pandemic situation of corona is everywhere, and people live in terrible fear and anxiety. What is my role in this epidemic situation when I keep myself ‘secured’ from the unhealthy surroundings? My act could be justified as a lawful citizen to abide the directives of the civil authority. However, when thousands of people live in fright and fretfulness, is it really justifiable? Given my situation, what else can I do? It is here the request to pray for others reverberates in my ears. Can I take ‘praying for others’ as a mission? What is the meaning of intercession? Is prayer of intercession theologically sound? Is prayer of intercession intelligible? This short reflection tries to answer these questions by taking Jesus’ prayer in Lk 10:21 as a foundation.

Situating the Context

In Lk 10:21 we have the instance of Jesus praying to the Father: “At that very moment he rejoiced in the Holy Spirit and said: I give you praise, Father, Lord of heaven and earth, for although you have hidden these things from the wise and the learned you have revealed them to the childlike. Yes, Father, such has been your gracious will”. Here we see a contrast between the learned, the wise, and the childlike. While the learned and the wise pretend to understand the mystery of the Kingdom of God, to the childlike it has been revealed

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as they ready to accept the things of the Kingdom of God with the easiness of a child.

Paul articulates this idea very strongly in 1 Cor 1:21: “Since ... the world did not know God through wisdom, it was the will of God through the foolishness of the proclamation to save those who have faith”.... “For the foolishness of God is wiser than human wisdom, and the weakness of God is stronger than human strength.” Similar texts are to be found also in the Hebrew Bible as well, for instance Isa 29:14: “The wisdom of its men shall perish and the understanding of its prudent men be hid,” or Isa 19:11-12: “Utter fools are the prince of Zoan! The wisest of Pharaoh’s advisers give stupid counsel. Where are your wise men? Let them tell you and make known. What the Lord of Hosts has planned.”

So, in all these texts we can see that the wise and the learned are either kept dubious about the power of prayer or questioned the futility of their wisdom, while the childlike is praised for their trust and reliance in the Lord.

The Wise, the Learned and the Prayer of Intercession

The prayer of intercession is among the things which the wise and the learned are inclined to consider as meaningless and even absurd. Certainly the learned and the wise will not object to the primary meaning of the Latin term “*intercedere*”, ‘to walk in the middle,’ ‘ready to help each one of the two parties’ or ‘to interpose oneself in favor of one of them.’ There are many examples of this in the Bible,

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for instance Joseph asking the chief cupbearer of the king of Egypt to remember him when he will be out of the prison and to speak on his favor to the Pharaoh (Gen 40:14). That is to say, a man or woman can speak on behalf of a fellow man or woman to a third person because this third person can change his mind and a wise intercession may help him to make the right decision or to reverse the wrong decision.

Can this meaning of “*intercedere*” be applied to the prayer of intercession? We believe that God does not make wrong decisions, and therefore, when we come to the prayer of intercession, we ‘stay before God for another person,’ asking him to intervene and modify his/her situation on behalf of that person. Naturally, this would raise objections in the mind of the learned and the wise. They tend to ask: Is not the mind of God right and unchangeable from the beginning? Then, how can God be moved to change his mind and to reverse a wrong decision? We too do sometimes belong to this category, when we think that the prayer of intercession remains somewhere in the air and does not produce fruit, or when we consider it as a second class devotion to which may be given sometimes some scraps of time. In fact God generally gives a help with the free collaboration of the interested person. Here comes the role of the intercessor who is ‘childlike.’

The ‘Childlike’ and the Prayer of Intercession

Against the learned and the wise stands the childlike who receives the gift of intercession ‘to stand before God for another’ (Lk 10:21).

We are “responsible to all men for all and everything, for all human sins, national and individual. For know, dear ones, that everyone of us is undoubtedly responsible for all men and everything on earth, not merely through the general sinfulness of creation, but each one personally for all mankind and every individual man.” –
Fyodor Dostoevsky

We can see many examples for this in the Bible: Abraham prayed in order to avert the punishment of Sodom (Gen 18:22-32); Moses interceded for the entire people of Israel (Exod 32:11-13), and also for an individual, like his sister Miriam (Num 12:13); Samuel, who even after breaking with the people, promised to keep interceding for them (1 Sam 12:23) to David, who asked for the life of his son (2 Sam 12:16-17); Amos prayed to the Lord to forgive Jacob, because “he is so small” (Amos 7:1-6); Jeremiah exhorted the people in exile to pray for the welfare of the city to which they were brought (Jer 29:7) etc. We are invited to enter in to the heart of these great intercessors so that we may understand the value of intercession.

The dictionary gives the meaning of ‘childlike’ as an adult having the qualities, such as innocence, trust, and ingenuousness associated with a child, or resembling qualities appropriate to a child or childhood. The gospels tell us how Jesus calls, commissions, and heal children. One of the most powerful Gospel stories is where Jesus insists that children in the crowd be brought to him for blessing (cf. Mk 10:13-16.). Jesus was completely furious with his disciples for keeping the children away from him. His deliberate act of blessing children, the lowliest of the low, is a powerful sign and a political act about how his kingdom works. But Jesus goes further than this by suggesting that ‘whoever does not receive the kingdom of God as a little child will never enter it’ (Lk 18:17).

In short, Jesus says that we must learn from children; they tell us important things about our own spiritual health. They can show us how to pray especially when we pray for others, i.e. with innocence, trust, simplicity and ingenuousness. We are called to intercede to the Lord for others like a child.

Meaning of the Prayer of Intercession

Both the Old Testament and New Testament tell us very clearly that God wants us to care for our neighbor. God wants us to

have not only what we call solidarity with others, but also he wants a real concern for each other, a care which represents the care of God for each one of us. He is ready to ask anyone of us with the primordial question which was first posed to Cain: "Where is your brother? Where is your sister? This is clearly expressed in the parable of the last judgment, in the Gospel of Matthew 25:31-46, where the Lord says to those who have helped the neighbor "You did to me" (25:40). He is then present in all the loving deeds, in all the acts of forgiveness, in the commitment of those who fight against violence, hatred, famine, suffering and so on.

Those who have the gift of intercession see God's light in the face of every human being. In other words we could say that they see the world as a great net of relationship, or, in the computer's language, a web where everyone is dependent to the other. This is strongly expressed in the words of Staretz Zossima, one of the key figures in the masterpiece of Dostoevsky's *The Brothers Karamazov*: "Love God's people. Because we have come here and shut ourselves within these walls" in order to realize that we are "not only worse than others", but that we are "responsible to all men for all and everything, for all human sins, national and individual. For know, dear ones, that everyone of us is undoubtedly responsible for all men and everything on earth, not merely through the general sinfulness of creation, but each one personally for all mankind and every individual man. This knowledge is the crown of life for the monk and every man. Only through that knowledge, our heart grows with infinite, universal, inexhaustible love. Then everyone of you will have the power to win over the whole world by love and to wash away the sins of the world with your tears". And he concludes: "Be proud neither to the little nor to the great. Hate not those who reject you, who insult you, who abuse and slander you. Hate not the atheist, the teachers of evil, the materialists - and I mean not only the good ones - for there are many good ones among them, especially in our day- hate not even the wicked ones. Remember them in your prayer thus: Save, O Lord, all those who have none to

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pray for them, save all those who will not pray. And add: it is not in pride that I make this prayer, O Lord, for I am lower than all men ..."

Certainly this interdependence and necessary interconnection, by which every one of us is bound to all others, is a deep spiritual mystery. Prayer of intercession helps us to recognize little by little this mutual belonging, which has to characterize all our actions according to the commandment "You shall love your neighbor as yourself" (Lev 19:18). Moreover, prayers of intercession help to us understand how much everything was woven and kept together by the Lord for a greater web of relationship.

From the above discussion, it is quite certain that the prayer of intercession is not to obtain a change in God's will, but to let the creature have part in the gifts of God. God graciously allows us to desire what he wants us to give, and we express it through the intercessory prayers. However, as we have seen above, there is much more than this. God wants us to be for one another, showing interest, compassion, charity, mutual help, and love in everything. Prayer of intercession exercises this mutual responsibility towards one another. God wants us to create a great unity in mankind, and this unity is actualized by the prayer of intercession. Thus, through the prayers of intercession a full communion is realized among human beings. Those who can do something for the other in the physical sense are called to do it, and all others are invited to unite their prayer in a great intercession. And we have a model in Jesus Christ, who "lives forever to make intercession" for us (Hebr 7:25; Rom 8:34).

Of course, the intercession presupposes that the person who does it is accepted by the Lord, is in a sense his friend, as it is said of Abraham, to whom God does not want to hide anything of what he is about to do (Gen 18:17). The intercessor is somebody who chooses to live according to God's project. He

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is a person who really cares for his brothers and sisters and wishes that they live according to God's will. Therefore the presence of many intercessors is also a way for the realization of a community which corresponds to God's plan.

Conclusion

The prayer of intercession appears as nonsense to the people who look only to this world, and it is also not understood by those who measure everything by the yard stick of physical effectiveness and of visible fruit. The prayer of intercession is a gift of the Spirit of God who works for the unity of God's plan for humanity. The prayer of intercession is a consequence of the law of mutual belonging and of mutual responsibility. It looks to the unity of mankind by giving to each one the invitation to participate to the difficulties and trials of every human being. The prayer of intercession is an expression of the structure of being, in which the primacy is not that of the person who cares for his own identity and well-being, but that of the person-in relation, who cares for the being of other.

So, in this time of corona pandemic, one way of keeping the suffering humanity close to our heart, to express our solidarity with the victims of corona virus pandemic is to raise our hearts and voices to the Lord who is the sovereign of the heaven and the earth. In short, the challenge before us at this crucial time is to be an intercessor for the world, especially for those who are affected and afflicted by this pandemic situation.